

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-294-IG-1% (0.1%AcOH)	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	104	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	4 294
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	270.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 270.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/3/2023 3:25:37 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/12/2023 10:04:34 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	30.072	1996077	35.20	34922
2	32.135	2001150	35.29	32518
3	41.533	834007	14.71	11821
4	43.872	838807	14.79	11265

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-295-IG-1% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	104	Acq. Method Set:	1%210400
Injection #:	2	Processing Method:	LRM 4 295
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	270.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 270.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/3/2023 4:17:16 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/4/2023 9:47:44 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	29.861	459	0.04	63
2	32.028	1151803	98.30	20785
3	41.389	18961	1.62	317
4	43.715	510	0.04	85